

Title: DEF FUNCTION(DYSTOPIAKIRA)

1. PROGRAM NOTES

Neo Tokyo, ca. 2019, 31 years after World War III, Akira awakens. This homage is an audiovisual, live-coded performance, remixing and re-envisioning the 1988 classic film created in the year of its setting, 2019 and reimagined now in 2022/2023 as the audiovisual work *DEF FUNCTION(DYSTOPIAKIRA)*.

The authors use the code editor Jensaarai to collaboratively and simultaneously live-code TidalCycles and Python, each supported by SuperCollider and Touch Designer on the backend respectively. The authors often collaborate remotely due to their respective locations which is facilitated by Jensaarai. This enables the client-side rendering of both audio and visuals in order to retain high-quality representations of both elements.

Fig. 1. Screenshot from demonstration video

2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

DEF FUNCTION(DYSTOPIAKIRA) is a live-coded meditation on the film Akira. An ideal performance duration is 10-20 minutes or more and the venue type is entirely open. Technical requirements include :

- One 6 foot-long table (approximately)
- 2 chairs

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- Stereo audio (quarter-inch jacks)
- Projector and projection screen
- HDMI connection to projector

Ideally the performers are situated in such a way that the audience sees the projection screen behind the performers.

3. MEDIA LINK(S)

- Audio and Video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iBXioiTitL4>

ETHICAL STANDARDS

Please note, that if any elements of the submitted work involve research with people or animals, authors should include a section “Compliance with Ethical Standards” before the References, including (if relevant): information regarding sources of funding, potential conflicts of interest (financial or non-financial), informed consent if the research involved human participants, statement on welfare of animals if the research involved animals.